

SYNTHESIS OF *PARA*-AMIDINOPHENYLSTIBINIC ACID

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In an attempt to obtain compounds of enhanced therapeutic activity and low toxicity for the treatment of Kala-azar, *p*-amidinophenylstibinic acid has now been synthesised.

The direct trypanocidal action of synthalin (decamethylenediguanidine dihydrochloride) was first demonstrated by Lourie and Yorke (*Ann. Trop. Med. Parasit.*, 1937, 31, 435). Later King, Lourie and Yorke (*Lancet*, 1937, 233, 130) prepared and examined a number of compounds related to synthalin and found that symmetrical diamidinoalkanes exhibited an even greater trypanocidal action than that of the corresponding guanidino derivatives. In view of these observations, a large number of aromatic diamidines has been synthesised by Ashley, Barber, Ewins, Newbery and Self (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 103) in the hope that such compounds may exhibit increased trypanocidal action. Among the aromatic diamidines, synthesised by these workers, 4:4'-diamidinostilbene and 4:4'-diamidinodiphenoxypentane have been successfully employed for the treatment of Mediterranean Kala-azar (Kirk and Sati, *Ann. Trop. Med. Parasit.*, 1940, 34, 82; Kirk and MacDonald, *ibid.*, 1940, 34, 131) and of Indian Kala-azar (Adams and Yorke, *ibid.*, 1939, 33, 323; 1940, 34, 174). This discovery has opened up a new vista in the chemotherapy of Kala-azar.

Derivatives of *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid, such as, urea stibamine, diethylamine-*p*-aminophenylstibinate, etc., have been found to be potent drugs for the treatment of Kala-azar. Although the former drug is widely used in India for the treatment of Kala-azar, it has two drawbacks, namely, its variable constitution and its instability. Moreover, this drug at times does show toxic reaction. In an attempt to obtain compounds of enhanced therapeutic activity and low toxicity for the treatment of Kala-azar, it has been considered to be of great interest to synthesise and pharmacologically examine *p*-amidinophenylstibinic acid, a compound containing both the amidino and phenylstibinic acid groups.

Pure *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid is diazotised and the diazo solution treated with cuprous cyanide solution when *p*-cyanophenylstibinic acid (I) is formed. The cyano compound has been purified by trituration with glacial acetic acid which dissolves any unreacted *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid. The compound (I) is hydrolysed by concentrated alkali to *p*-carboxyphenylstibinic acid (II). The cyano compound (I) has been converted into *p*-amidinophenylstibinic acid (III) via the corresponding imino-ether (cf. Linsker and Bogert, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 65, 932)

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Cyanophenylstibinic Acid (I).—*p*-Aminophenylstibinic acid, prepared according to the well known method of Dunning and Reid (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 48, 2959; American Patent, No. 1682269), is always contaminated with varying quantities of *p*-acetylaminophenylstibinic acid (Gray, Trevan, Bainbridge and Atwood, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1931, B, 108, 54). Both *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid and its acetyl derivative are readily soluble in glacial acetic acid; the former, however, slowly dissolves in dilute hydrochloric acid, in which the acetyl derivative is insoluble. The amino compound was therefore purified by trituration with a large excess of *N*/4-hydrochloric acid, filtration, treatment of the filtrate with concentrated alkali till faintly acidic, and finally by precipitation with sodium acetate. This operation was carried out twice and the *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid, thus obtained in a pure form, was kept in a slightly moist condition before was used, otherwise it tended to decompose in a dry state.

Pure *p*-aminophenylstibinic acid (50 g.) was treated with hydrochloric acid (750 c.c.) and diazotised, under ice-cooling, with 3*N*-sodium nitrite solution (67 c.c.). The diazonium chloride solution was slowly poured, under brisk stirring, into a warm (70°) solution of copper sulphate (50 g.), potassium cyanide (56 g.) and water (300 c.c.) and the mixture was kept in a cold room overnight. Next day, the mixture was filtered and then concentrated under reduced pressure to a volume of 125 c.c. After adding 20 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid, *p*-cyanophenylstibinic acid was filtered and washed with hydrochloric acid and then with water. The solid was dried in air and then triturated with glacial acetic acid, filtered, washed with excess of water and dried in air, yield 10 g. The solid was further purified by solution in dilute alkali and reprecipitation with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. It is soluble in hot water, from which it is obtained as a colourless powder, which does not melt even at 320°. (Found: N, 4.78; Sb, 43.98. $C_7H_4O_2NSb$ requires N, 5.11; Sb, 44.47 per cent). It is insoluble in dilute acids but readily soluble in alkali, and does not contain any diazotisable amino group.

The solid mixed with cuprous cyanide, as described above, was thoroughly triturated with an excess of 10% hydrochloric acid, filtered, washed with water and dried. The solid was next triturated with excess of glacial acetic acid, filtered and washed with water. The compound (5 g.) was proved to be *p*-cyanophenylstibinic acid after purification as described above.

Carboxyphenylstibinic Acid (II).—The above compound (I, 5g.) was heated on the wire-gauze under reflux with 27% sodium hydroxide solution (60 c.c.) for 3 hours, when ammonia was evolved. The solution was cooled in ice and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitate was filtered and washed thoroughly with water. It is insoluble in hot water and in ordinary organic solvents. It was purified by solution in alkali and precipitation with hydrochloric acid, when, on drying *in vacuo* at 130° for 3 hours, a white powder was obtained which did not melt even at 320°, yield 3g. [Found: Sb, 41.28; M.W. (by titration), 288. $C_7H_4O_3Sb$ requires Sb, 41.59 per cent. M. W., 292.76]. It does not contain any nitrogen and is found to form di-sodium salt, as determined by

titration with standard sodium hydroxide solution till a neutral reaction is obtained (phenolphthalein as indicator).

p-Amidinophenylstibinic Acid (III).— The above compound (I, 10 g.) was finely powdered and suspended in dry ether (20 g.), to which absolute alcohol (8 g.) was added. The mixture was then saturated with dry hydrochloric acid gas at 0° and the flask was then well-stoppered and left in a refrigerator for 6 days, when the imino-ether hydrochloride separated as a grey powder, which was filtered off, washed with dry ether and dried in a vacuum desiccator, yield 8.5 g. It does not melt even at 300°.

The above imino-ether hydrochloride (8 g.) was finely powdered and treated with 10% alcoholic ammonia (60 c.c), and the mixture was heated in a closed vessel at 60-65° for 5 hours. After cooling overnight, the chocolate coloured precipitate of the amidine hydrochloride was filtered, washed with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator. It does not melt even at 300°. It was then triturated with very dilute hydrochloric acid and the solution after filtration was carefully treated with dilute ammonium hydroxide, when a brown amorphous precipitate of the free amidine was obtained. The addition of dilute ammonium hydroxide was continued till maximum precipitation was obtained. The solid (3g.) was purified by solution in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitation with just the requisite quantity of ammonia. It was filtered, washed with water, and dried. (Found: N, 9.24; Sb, 42.18. $C_7H_6O_2N_2$ Sb requires N, 9.63; Sb, 41.87 per cent). It is soluble both in dilute mineral acids and alkalis but practically insoluble in hot water and in ordinary organic solvents, and does not melt even at 300°.

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